

International Study Programmes in Design Management ***Monitoring Report November 2018 – January 2019***

By Claudia Ramseier, January 31, 2019
Research Associate Bachelor Design Management, International

Management Summary

Since 2015, Design Management, International (DMI) annually conducts a comparative study on the international landscape of Design Management study programmes to provide an overview on Bachelor's, Master's and other courses in the mentioned field. In this study, all programmes, which seek to bring together the design and business disciplines are taken into account. The main objectives are to monitor development trends in this still rather young discipline, to define universities with Bachelor's degrees with the aim to establish student exchange and to enlist viable consecutive Master's programmes for DMI graduates. A long-term aim is to build an international network of universities that offer such programmes and to contribute to fostering Design Management as an academic discipline.

The 2018 study showed that there have been only slight changes in the educational landscape for Design Management training since 2017. The total number of available degree programmes (122 in 2018) remained stable with a slight increase since 2015. However, it can be observed that many short term programmes such as postgraduate or professional courses have been closed: in 2015, the list included 30 postgraduate and other shortterm courses, today it is only 10. At the same time, the number of Bachelor's (from 14 to 22) and Master's (from 69 to 87) degree programmes has increased by about a third. In summary, it can be said that 71 percent of the Design Management study programs are offered at Master's level. Concerning the curricula structures or specific addressed subject areas in the field of Design Management, no significant changes could be observed since the 2015 study.

For 2018, ten Bachelor's programmes have been defined, who meet the set criteria: comparable to the DMI curriculum, taking into account existing partner universities of Lucerne School of Art and Design, feasibility of exchange in terms of contractual requirements, international reputation of university, language (English or German). In addition, ten Master's programmes have been define according to the following criteria: consecutive programme with a specific focus that connects to the DMI tracks in Communication and Product Design Management, international reputation of university, language (English or German).

Table of Contents

Management Summary	1
1 Introduction	3
2 Research Criteria	4
3 International Study Programmes in Design Management.....	5
4 Bachelor's Programmes for Student Exchange	7
5 Consecutive Master's Programmes.....	8
6 References	10
7 Appendix	11
<i>List of International Design Management Study Programmes.....</i>	<i>11</i>

1 Introduction

This report summarizes the comparative study on the international landscape of Design Management programmes which was conducted from October 2018 to January 2019 and contains an update of the large-scale survey conducted in 2015¹ as well as the update of the programme list of Design Management study programmes in 2017. Core objective of this annually conducted study is to monitor and compare the international landscape in the said field and to keep a comprehensive list of study programmes and courses, which include Bachelor's, Master's and PhD programmes as well as different (postgraduate) certificate, graduate and leadership programmes or any other shortterm courses. This list will be published online and made accessible to students seeking for exchange or consecutive programmes as well as to higher education professionals and any other interested stakeholders working in the field of Design Management.

The initial goal of the analysis in 2015 was to provide an overview of the worldwide Bachelor's and Master's programmes in the wider subject area of Design Management and related disciplines. However, for the 2017 and 2018 survey, the research criteria have been slightly adapted. The data collected in 2015 have been reviewed and analyzed with the set criteria for 2017 and 2018, in order to get a consistent picture of the development of the educational landscape in design management. On the one hand, the term «Design Management» is defined within this context in a narrower sense than before, which means that the study includes exclusively study programmes with a core focus on Design Management, e.g programmes that seek to bring together both the design and business disciplines. Programmes in related fields that offer single Design Management or Design Thinking courses, tracks or Design Management as a minor, but which as a whole are either design or business/management training, have not been considered. This is due to the fact, that the present survey is conducted with the objective to define possible partner universities who offer Bachelor's programmes for student exchange or other institutional partnerships and which are eligible on a contractual basis.² In addition, viable consecutive Master's programmes for DMI graduates are listed as well. Another reason for restricting the research criteria is that the study is intended to contribute to the development and promotion of the Design Management discipline.

The key questions for the present study were:

1. How many new programmes have been established and on what level of study?
2. Are there any new trends or changes in the landscape of Design Management Educational programmes that can be observed since 2015?
3. Which universities may be considered for an exchange on Bachelor level?
4. Which ten Master's programmes are viable consecutive options for DMI graduates?

¹ Ramseier, Claudia (2015). Internationale Bachelor-Studienprogramme im Bereich Design Management: Vergleichsstudie (Bericht). Hochschule Luzern – Design und Kunst, Bachelor Design Management, International, Luzern.

² Such as Erasmus partners, according to the current negotiation options of Lucerne School of Art and Design.

2 Research Criteria

International Design Management Study Programmes

1. The study takes into account all types of degree programmes: BA-, MA-, PhD-, CAS-, MAS-, MBA- and PhD- programmes; Certificate, Graduate and Leadership programmes, Postgraduate courses
2. The study takes into account all study programmes whose curricula cover the fields of Design & Management and seek to combine them.

International Bachelor's Programmes for Exchange Partnerships

1. The study takes into account BA programmes that are suitable for an exchange semester for DMI students which are comparable in content to the DMI curriculum, taking into account existing partner universities of the HSLU.
2. The study takes into account the feasibility of student exchanges in terms of contractual requirements, e.g. places a particular focus on public higher education institutions within the European Erasmus network.
3. The study takes into account Bachelor's programmes with an international reputation according to the position on international university rankings³ (Top 500 universities).
4. The study takes into account Bachelor's programmes that are taught in English or German.

10 Consecutive Master's Programmes for DMI Graduates

1. The study takes into account 10 consecutive Master's programmes in Design Management that offer a continuing Design Management education with a specific, thematic focus, which connects to the DMI tracks in Communication and Product Design Management.
2. The study takes into account Master's programmes with an international reputation according to their position on international university rankings⁴ (Top 500 universities).
3. The study takes into account Master's programmes that are taught in English or German.

³ Several international university rankings have been consulted, cf. chapter 6 References.

⁴ Several international university rankings have been consulted, cf. chapter 6 References.

3 International Study Programmes in Design Management

Since the last data collection in 2017, no significant changes in numbers of Design Management programmes could be observed. The overall number of programmes has slightly decreased from 124 in 2017 to 122 in 2018, but generally increased since 2015.

As in the previous years, most of the programmes are offered in Europe, where the mother country of Design Management, the UK (26 programmes) and Germany (11 programmes) still offer most of the Design Management study programmes.

The most significant changes to be observed since 2015 are the general increase of Bachelor's and Master's programmes and the decrease of programmes assigned to the category "other" (graduate/postgraduate certificates/diplomas and shortterm courses). As before, the vast majority of Design Management programmes are offered on a Master's level.

Between 2017 and 2018, 7 Master's programmes have been closed and 7 new ones opened.⁵ Three of the universities who offer new (consecutive) Master's degrees since 2018 already had a Bachelor's programme before: Swinburne University of Technology introduced a Master's and two graduate programmes (certificate, diploma), London University of the Arts introduced an MBA (in addition to three Master's programmes), Parsons introduced an Executive Master's degree. United International Business Schools introduced Design Management as a new field of study with both a new Bachelor's and Master's degree. On the other hand, both Birmingham City University and Srishti School of Art, Design & Technology offer a Bachelor's programme in addition to different Master's programmes since 2018.

At the same time, two thirds of the postgraduate and short-term vocational certificate and diploma programmes (categorized as "other") have been closed. While some universities (Paris College of Art, Sichuan University of Fine Arts) have completely removed Design Management from their curricular agenda, others have removed shorter courses and developed Bachelor's and Master's programmes instead. Parsons, for example, closed its graduate certificate programme and opened an executive Master's programme. Birmingham City University closed its two Postgraduate programmes (diploma and certificate course) and opened a Design Management Bachelor's programme. It can thus be observed that the number of postgraduate continuing education programmes has decreased significantly and there is a tendency towards the establishment of Master's programmes.

As in the previous years, the vast majority of Design Management Programmes are offered at design and art schools as well as at full universities with design and/or technology departments. There are in all ten business schools that offer Design Management degrees.

Concerning specific subject areas in the field, no significant changes could be observed since 2015. The main addressed topics can be summarized as before: innovation (management), service/product/experience/media design, entrepreneurship and business, (project) management, marketing, (business/design) strategy, sustainability. There are 5 programmes, which put a focus on the fashion industry. The field remains elusive, which is also reflected in the still various denominations of the degrees. 21 of 122 programmes are called "Design Management". There is still no common agreement on how to name the field that combines the business and design disciplines, as shows the following list of the most common denominations of Design Management study programmes⁶:

Business & Design; Business Design; Design & Business; Design & Branding (Strategy); Design Business Management; Design Innovation Management; Design Management & Entrepreneurship; Design Management Innovation; Design Management, Strategy & Entrepreneurship; Design Strategies; Design Strategy; Design Strategy & Management; Design Strategy & Innovation; Design, Innovation & Entrepreneurship; Entrepreneurial Design & Management; Entrepreneurial Design Management; Entrepreneurship & Business Design; Entrepreneurship & Innovation; Innovation and Design; Innovation by Design; Innovation Strategies & Entrepreneurship; Integrated Design & Management; International Management & Design Innovation; Management by Design; Strategic Design & Management; Strategic Design Management; System Design & Management.

⁵ Closed: Srishti School of Art, Design & Technology (M.Des. Strategic Design & Brand Leadership), Northumbria University (MA/MSc Multidisciplinary Design Innovation), Lancaster University (MSc International Innovation), IED Barcelona (MA Sustainable Product Design: Innovation & Management), University of the Arts London (Mdes Service Experience Design & Innovation), Carnegie Mellon (MA Integrated Innovation), Kendall College of Art and Design (MBA Design Innovation Management).

New: United Intl. Business Schools (MA Design Management), Swinburne University (MA Design Strategy and Innovation), HfG Schwäbisch Gmünd (MA Strategische Gestaltung – Schwerpunkt Management), Hochschule macromedia (MA Design Management), Mediadesign Hochschule (MA Design Management), University of the Arts London (MBA Birkbeck), Parsons (Global Executive MA Strategic Design and Management).

⁶ E.g. study programmes that are comparable to DMI.

However, one interesting observation could be made when comparing the current data with the programme descriptions from 2015. While in 2015, many programme descriptions in general referred to the development of products or services, it is rather new that in more programme descriptions, the term and concept of “design” are understood – and explicitly communicated – in a broader sense, implicitly referring to the "third and forth order of Design"⁷

*Design represents a valuable strategic asset – the tools and the processes to problem-solve and innovate. The management of that asset, the ability to understand, optimize, and steer that energy is becoming vital to an organization’s internal and external success.*⁸

4 Bachelor’s Programmes for Student Exchange

For 2018, 22 Design Management Bachelors’ programmes could be defined, of which 16 are located in Europe, two in Asia, two in the USA, one in Australia and one is an international programme with campus locations in Switzerland, Japan and the USA. The study programmes usually last three to four years fulltime (often with part-time options) and are taught either in English or German.

Regarding the curricula, learning objectives and career prospects, the listed Bachelor’s programmes are all quite similar to the DMI programme concerning the basic course structure and addressed topics. The focus ranges from learning practical design skills such as sketching, model building, design (research) methods, CAD to the development of business fundamentals and design (management) theory. In addition, subjects are taught that serve personal and communicative competency development, such as scientific writing or oral communication skills. However, some of the programmes focus on specific fields such as communication, product design, technology or the fashion industry. The "Brüder Grimm Berufsakademie Hanau" constitutes an exception, as the programme combines college studies with a vocational education (e.g. an apprenticeship), which is completed with a Bachelor’s degree.

With regard to the intensification of the student exchange at DMI, ten programmes have been defined, which meet the set criteria:

Partner universities of Lucerne School of Art and Design

1. Srishti School of Art, Design and Technology, Bangalor
Focus on future technologies (internet of things etc.)
[B. Des. Business Services and System Design](#)
2. Fachhochschule Salzburg GmbH (FHS)
Focus on furniture manufacturing
[BA Design- und Produktmanagement](#)

⁷ Richard Buchanan. *Design Research and the New Learning*. Design Issues: Volume 17. Number 4, Autumn 2001.

⁸ University of Bridgeport, MPS Design Management. <http://www.bridgeport.edu/academics/schools-colleges/shintaro-akatsu-school-design/design-management-mps>. Access on January 30, 2019. Similar statements are made for example by OCAD University (MDes Strategic Foresight and Innovation) or Miami International University of Art & Design (MA Design & Media Management).

3. VIA University College
Special exchange semester programme for foreign students
[BA Design & Business](#)
4. Inholland University
[BA Business Innovation](#)

Programmes that focus on the core topics of the two current DMI Tracks (Communication and Product Design Management)

1. Lancaster University
[BSc Hons Marketing and Design](#)
2. London University of the Arts, London college of Communication (LCC)
Focus on communication, media, design and global cultures
[BA \(Hons\) Design Management](#)
3. Fachhochschule Salzburg GmbH (FHS)
Focus on furniture manufacturing
[BA Design- und Produktmanagement](#)

Universities with international reputation

1. Carnegie Mellon: Tepper School of Business, Integrative Design, Arts & Technology Network
[Undergraduate programme Innovation & Entrepreneurship - Ideate](#)
2. Parsons School of Design
[BBA Strategic Design and Management](#)
3. Lancaster University
[BSc Hons Marketing and Design](#)
4. Birmingham City University
[BA Hons Design Management](#)

5 Consecutive Master's Programmes

For 2018, 87 Master's Programmes in the field of Design Management could be defined, of which 8 programmes are offered by partner universities of Lucerne School of Art and Design. The majority of programmes are still offered in North America (20 programmes) and the UK (21). Unlike the Bachelor's programmes, most of the Master's concentrate on a specific thematic focus, only 20 programmes offer a general Design Management Master's.

The main focus in most of the programmes lies on design strategy, leadership and innovation management. Depending on the university, some curricula are engineering and technology-based. Many programmes offer a specialization (track or major) in certain specific topics, of which the most

represented are: service, experience & systems design; sustainability; communication, media, marketing & branding; government and urban studies; social innovation; fashion and luxury industries.⁹

With regard to the above set criteria, 10 consecutive Master's programmes could be defined:

1. Aalto University, School of Arts, Design and Architecture
[MA International Design Business Management](#)
Graduates of this programme earn a degree either in business, design or technology.
2. Carnegie Mellon: Tepper School of Business
[MA Integrated Innovation for Products & Services](#)
This course focuses on future product & services, that merge technologies and humanity.
3. Glasgow School of Art (GSA)
[MDes Design Innovation & Citizenship or Collaborative Creativity or Service Design](#)
This course with several specializations focuses on Design in the public sector.
4. Hochschule RheinMain Wiesbaden
[MA Media & Design Management](#)
Strong focus on communication and media sciences.
5. Köln International School of Design (KISD)
[MEDes European Design](#)
Encompassing design education embedded in a network of seven leading European design schools (Aalto, Glasgow School of Art, KISD; Politecnico di Milano, ENSCI Les Ateliers, University of Aveiro, Konstfack). Core topics: design theory and research, design strategy & leadership, social & collaborative design, craftsmanship, sustainability.
6. Massachusetts Institute of Technology MIT
[MS Integrated Design & Management \(IDM\)](#)
This course combines Design, Engineering and Business, with strong focus on engineering.
7. Novia University of Applied Sciences
[MA Business Administration, Leadership and Service Design](#)
Focus on Service Design.
8. Parsons The New School for Design
[MS Strategic Design and Management](#)
This course focuses on the development of business leadership qualities.
9. PrattInstitute
[MPS Design Management](#)
Professional Master's programme with a strong focus on strategic leadership.
10. University of the Arts London, Central Saint Martins
[MBA Birkbeck](#)
Focus on cross-disciplinary collaboration, creative approaches and social engagement in management and leadership activities.

⁹ TU Delft stands out with a specific track called "Medesign", which focuses on public healthcare systems within in the Master's programme in Strategic Product Design.

6 **References**

Businessinsider.com – The world’s 25 best design schools

<https://www.businessinsider.com/the-worlds-25-best-design-schools-2012-11?r=US&IR=T>

Access on January 10, 2019.

Cumulus. International Association of Universities and Colleges of Art, Design and Media: Members. <http://www.cumulusassociation.org/members/full-members>

Access on December 12, 2018.

Design Management Institute: List of Universities

https://www.dmi.org/page/What_is_Design_Manag

Access on December 12, 2018.

Hochschule Luzern: Partnerhochschulen.

<https://www.hslu.ch/de-ch/design-kunst/ueber-uns/international/partnerschulen/>

Access on January 31, 2019.

Quartz: The world’s best design schools, ranked.

<https://qz.com/645890/uk-and-us-schools-dominate-design-school-rankings/>

Access on January 10, 2019.

Ranker.com: The 30 Best Design Schools in the World

https://www.ranker.com/list/best-30-design-programs-in-the-world/college-info?var=12&utm_expid=16418821-253.BAWaw7_5T3qAVTf7EdWDtA.1

Accessed on October 10, 2018.

Shanghai Ranking

<http://www.shanghairanking.com/Shanghairanking-Subject-Rankings/index.html#>

Access on December 12, 2018.

Studyportals

<http://www.mastersportal.eu>

Access on December 5, 2018.

Study in Denmark

<https://studyindenmark.dk>

Access on December 12, 2018.

Study in Portugal

<http://studyinportugal.net>

Access on January 11, 2019.

SI-UK. Study in the UK. UK university rankings 2019.

<http://www.studyin-uk.com/uk-study-info/university-rankings/>

Access on January 15, 2019.

The Guardian University Guide 2019. UK universities ranked by subject area: Design & crafts

<https://www.theguardian.com/education/ng-interactive/2018/may/29/university-guide-2019-league-table-for-design-crafts>

Access on January 15, 2019.

TimesHigherEducation

<https://www.timeshighereducation.com/>

Access on January 12, 2019.

Topuniversities.com: 10 top art & Design Schools 2018

<https://www.topuniversities.com/university-rankings-articles/university-subject-rankings/scholarships-study-10-top-art-design-schools-2018>

Accessed on October 10, 2018.

7 Appendix

List of International Design Management Study Programmes